

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

URIC ACID AND OTHER RISK FACTORS OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES IN HYPERTENSIVE PATIENTS IN SOUTHERN PART OF NIGERIA

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Abstract

Background: There is an increased prevalence of hypertension especially in low and middle-income countries. Hyperuricaemia is linked with an increased risk for hypertension, independent of typical risk factors of hypertension. Also, serum uric acid concentrations have been linked with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease. This study was aimed at evaluating the serum uric acid levels in hypertensive patients and comparing it with other risk factors of cardiovascular disease.

Methodology: This was a hospital-based cross-sectional study carried out between October 2022 and December 2023 at the Delta State Central Hospital, Warri. The study included 200 participants with hypertension and 100 healthy controls.

Results: Uric acid level ranged from 0.08 – 0.58 mmol/L in the hypertensives with a mean of 0.24 ± 0.11 mmol/L. In the controls, the mean value was 0.16 ± 0.07 mmol/L. The difference in mean was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Forty-two (21.0%) of the hypertensives compared to 5 (5.0%) of the controls had hyperuricaemia ($p = 0.005$). In the hypertensives, uric acid correlated positively with BMI ($r = 0.330$, $p = 0.001$) and weight circumference ($r = 0.263$, $p = 0.003$). Similarly, in the controls, there was a positive correlation between uric acid level and BMI ($r = 0.458$, $p = 0.001$).

Conclusion: Serum uric acid levels were significantly higher in the hypertensive patients than in the normotensive controls. There was a significant positive correlation between uric acid and BMI and WC in the hypertensive population and a significant positive correlation between uric acid and BMI in the controls.

Keywords: Hypertension. Uric acid, body mass index, estimated glomerular filtration rate, waist circumference.

Introduction

There is an increased prevalence of hypertension especially in low and middle-income countries.¹ Hyperuricaemia is linked with an increased risk for hypertension, independent of typical risk factors of hypertension.² Also, serum uric acid concentrations have been linked with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease.³ Thus, uric acid has been described as a potentially modifiable cardiovascular risk factor.⁴

The prevalence of hyperuricaemia has been shown to be higher in hypertensive subjects than in non-hypertensive subjects.⁵ Studies have reported

prevalence of hyperuricaemia in hypertensive subjects ranging from 9.1% to 37.33%.^{6,7}

Although, the cause of hypertension is uncertain in many patients, uric acid has been suggested to activate the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system which can cause injury to pre renal blood vessels.² In studies using animals, hyperuricaemia predisposes to hypertension by mechanisms that include inflammatory and vascular changes in the renal microcirculation, activation of the renin-angiotensin system and endothelial dysfunction.³ The reference intervals of serum uric acid in males and females are 3.5 to 7.2 mg/dl and 2.6-6.0 mg/dl

respectively.⁸ In premenopausal women, there is a lower serum urate level caused by the uricosuric effect of oestrogen. After menopause, serum uric acid level rises to levels comparable with males of similar age.⁹ Hyperuricaemia is caused by an imbalance between uric acid production and excretion.¹⁰ It has been defined as uric acid level greater than 7 mg/dl in males and greater than 6 mg/dl in females.¹¹ However, at lower thresholds of 4.7 mg/dl and 5.6 mg/dl respectively, serum uric acid has been documented to increase total mortality and cardiovascular mortality.¹² Acquired risk factors of hyperuricaemia and gout include ingestion of purine-rich foods like meat or seafood, ingestion of beverages and food with high content of sugar and intake of alcohol. Other risk factors of hyperuricaemia include hypertension, metabolic syndrome, chronic kidney disease, overweight and obesity.¹³ Uric acid is synthesized in the liver, adipose tissue and muscle.¹⁰ Uric acid is the final product of purine metabolism in humans.¹⁴ About two thirds of serum uric acid is generated in the body and the remaining from dietary purines. It is mainly a waste product that is excreted by the kidneys (70%) and intestines (30%).¹⁵ Studies comparing serum uric acid levels in hypertensive patients with other risk factors of cardiovascular disease is scarce in this environment. Hence, this study was aimed at evaluating the serum uric acid levels in hypertensive patients and comparing it with other risk factors of cardiovascular disease.

Methods

Research design and subjects

This was a hospital-based cross-sectional study carried out between October 2022 and December 2023 at the Delta State Central Hospital, Warri. Participants included in the study were individuals who were 18 years and older, diagnosed with hypertension (blood pressure \geq 140/90 mmHg) at the General Outpatient Department and the Cardiology Unit of the Delta State Central Hospital, Warri. Central Hospital Warri is a secondary health facility with 254 beds. They render general and specialized medical and surgical services.

Sample size estimation and sampling technique

The sample size was calculated from the formula for a cross-sectional study: $n = (Z^2Pq)/d^2$, where n

= sample size, Z = standard deviation, P = prevalence of hypertension, q = 1-P and d = degree of precision to be used (0.05). Consecutive sampling was used to recruit participants. The study included 200 participants with hypertension and 100 healthy controls. Participants with a history of diabetes mellitus, renal disease, malignancy and critically ill patients were excluded from the study. Written informed consent was obtained from each study participant. The study used a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire, which contained identification number, age, gender, weight, height, waist circumference, medical history and laboratory results. Body mass index (BMI) was determined from the weight (kg) divided by the height (meter) squared. Waist circumference (WC) was measured with the aid of a measuring tape at the approximate midpoint between the lower margin of the palpable rib and the top of the iliac crest.

Data collection

Five millilitres (5 ml) of blood was collected from each participant by venepuncture into a plain bottle and allowed to clot. The samples were separated and serum kept at -20°C until analysis. Morning and evening temperature recording were taken to monitor temperature of the freezer. Serum uric acid was analysed using enzymatic colorimetric method by Fortress Diagnostics. Serum creatinine was assayed on a spectrophotometer using the kinetic modification of the Jaffe procedure. Estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was predicted from serum creatinine using the Modification of Diet for Renal Disease formula based on age, sex, race and serum creatinine.¹⁶

Data analysis

Data was analysed with SPSS version 23. Continuous variables including age, blood pressure measurements and anthropometric variables, and biochemical parameters were tested for normality. Normally distributed continuous variables were summarized as mean, standard deviation, and ranges. Categorical variables were summarized using frequencies and percentages. The differences in means of continuous variables between the hypertensive group and controls were compared using the student T test. Chi square test was used for univariate analysis. The Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to correlate uric

acid with age, blood pressure measurements, BMI, waist circumference, serum creatinine and eGFR. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was done to determine predictors of hyperuricaemia. Statistical significance was set at <0.05 .

Ethical clearance

This study was approved by the ethics and research committee (protocol number: CHW/ECC VOL 1/276) of the Delta State Central Hospital, Warri. Written informed consent was obtained from each study participant and strict confidentiality was observed for participant's data.

Results

A total of 300 participants were enlisted for the study consisting of 200 hypertensives and 100 controls. The age range of the hypertensives was 19.0 – 92.0 years with a mean age and standard deviation of 58.2 ± 13.1 years and the controls had an age range of 22.0 – 66.0 years with a mean age and standard deviation of 43.8 ± 10.7 years. The hypertensives were significantly older than the controls ($p = 0.001$). The hypertensives included 147 (73.5%) females and 53 (26.5%) males while the controls included 53 (53.0%) females and 47 (47.0%) males. The difference in the sex distribution was also statistically significant ($p = 0.007$) (Table 1).

There was no significant difference in the body weight of the hypertensives and the controls as shown in table 1 (76.0 ± 18.0 vs. 76.2 ± 9.2 Kg respectively, $p = 0.946$). The body height also did not differ significantly between the hypertensives and controls (1.62 ± 0.07 vs. 1.64 ± 0.09 m, respectively, $p = 0.208$). Similarly, the BMI did not differ significantly between them (28.9 ± 6.5 vs. 28.8 ± 5.1 Kg/m², $p = 0.891$) (Table 2). Seventy-two (36.0%) of the hypertensives and 35 (35.0%) of the controls were obese (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²). The difference in proportion was not statistically significant ($p = 0.635$).

Only one study participant indicated smoking and the individual was among the controls. There was no significant difference in the distribution of smoking in the study groups ($p = 0.723$). Thirty three (16.5%) of the hypertensives drink alcohol compared to 7 (7.0%) of the controls and the difference in proportion was not statistically significant ($p = 0.104$).

Serum creatinine was higher in the hypertensives than in the controls but the difference in mean was not statistically significant (106.1 ± 97.2 vs. $88.4.0 \pm 17.7$ μ mol/l, $p = 0.073$). The mean eGFR was significantly higher in the hypertensive population than in the controls (1.3 ± 0.6 vs. 1.5 ± 0.4 ml/s/m², $p = 0.035$). Seventy-two (36.0%) of the hypertensive subjects had renal impairment (eGFR, < 1 ml/s/m²) compared to 32 (32.0%) of the controls. The difference in proportion was not statistically significant $p = 0.579$.

Figure 1: Boxplot showing the distribution of uric acid in the study population.

Uric acid level ranged from 0.08 – 0.58 mmol/L in the hypertensives with a mean of 0.24 ± 0.11 mmol/L. In the controls, the mean value was 0.16 ± 0.07 mmol/L. The difference in mean was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) Figure I. Forty-two (21.0%) of the hypertensives compared to 5 (5.0%) of the controls had hyperuricaemia ($p = 0.005$). (Figure 1).

In the hypertensives, uric acid correlated positively with BMI ($r = 0.330$, $p = 0.001$) and weight circumference ($r = 0.263$, $p = 0.003$) (Table 3). Similarly, in the controls, there was a positive correlation between uric acid level and BMI ($r = 0.458$, $p = 0.001$).

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of the study population

	Hypertensive n = 200	Controls n = 100	Statistical test	P-value
Age group				
<40	8 (4.0)	30 (30.0)		
40 – 59	97 (48.5)	63 (63.0)	* $\chi^2 = 38.830$	<0.001
≥60	95 (47.5)	7 (7.0)		
Sex				
Male	53 (26.5)	47 (47.0)	$\chi^2 = 7.200$	0.007
Female	147 (73.5)	53 (53.0)		
BMI				
Underweight	3 (1.5)	2 (2.0)	$\chi^2 = 0.675^*$	0.635
Normal	55 (27.5)	20 (20.0)		
Overweight	70 (35.0)	43 (43.0)		
Obese	72 (36.0)	35 (35.0)		
Alcohol intake	33 (16.5)	7 (7.0)	Fishers Exact	0.067
Smoking	0 (0.0)	1 (1.0)	Fishers Exact	0.333

*Adjusted Chi square test. BMI: body mass index

Table 2: Age, blood pressure measurements, anthropometrics and biochemical parameters of the study population.

	Hypertensive n= 200	Controls n = 100	T test	P-value
Age	58.2 ± 13.0	43.8 ± 10.7	t = 7.410	<0.001
	19.0 – 92.0	22.0 – 66.0		
SBP	169.2 ± 15.6	118.3 ± 11.9	t = 22.252	<0.001
	140.0 – 220.0	60.0 – 90.0		
DBP	106.5 ± 9.7	76.6 ± 7.4	t = 20.948	<0.001
	90.0 – 140.0	60.0 – 90.0		
Weight	76.0 ± 18.0	76.2 ± 9.2	t = -0.067	0.946
	44.0 – 135.0	59.0 – 106.0		
Height	1.62 ± 0.07	1.64 ± 0.09	t = -1.265	0.208
	1.50 – 1.80	1.45 – 1.80		
BMI	28.9 ± 6.5	28.8 ± 5.1	t = 0.137	0.891
	16.2 – 51.4	18.4 – 41.4		
Weight circumference	98.8 ± 13.2	91.3 ± 8.1	t = 4.056	<0.001
	70.0 – 149.0	80.0 – 129.0		
Creatinine	106.1 ± 97.2	88.4 ± 17.7	t = 1.802	0.073
	35.4 – 831.0	26.5 – 114.9		
eGFR	1.3 ± 0.6	1.5 ± 0.4	t = -2.126	0.035
	0.08 – 4.6	0.9 – 2.9		
Uric acid	0.24 ± 0.11	0.16 ± 0.07	t = 4.082	<0.001
	0.08 – 0.58	0.11 – 0.38		

SBP: systolic blood pressure; DBP: diastolic blood pressure; BMI: body mass index; eGFR: estimated glomerular filtration rate

Table 3: Correlation of uric acid levels with age, blood pressure measurements BMI, creatinine, eGFR, alcohol and smoking in hypertensives and controls.

		Hypertensives	Controls
Age	r	0.010	-0.075
	P-value	0.918	0.569
Sex	r	-0.058	0.015
	P-value	0.532	0.907
SBP	r	-0.154	0.184
	P-value	0.092	0.159
DBP	r	-0.010	0.234
	P-value	0.909	0.072
BMI	r	0.330	0.458
	P-value	0.001	0.001
Weight circumference	r	0.268	0.147
	P-value	0.003	0.261
Creatinine	r	-0.043	0.017
	P-value	0.640	0.897
eGFR	r	0.009	-0.049
	P-value	0.923	0.710

Dependent variable: Uric acid. SBP: systolic blood pressure; DBP: diastolic blood pressure; BMI: body mass index; eGFR: estimated glomerular filtration rate

Table 4: Multivariate regression analysis on hyperuricaemia on study group, age, sex, BMI eGFR, Smoking and Alcohol intake

	B	OR	95% CI	P-value
Group (HTN)	1.736	5.677	1.467 – 21.964	0.012
Age (≥ 60 yrs)	-0.827	0.437	0.162 – 1.178	0.102
Sex (M)	-1.238	0.290	0.088 – 0.951	0.041
BMI (Obesity)	1.541	4.669	1.896 – 11.496	0.001
eGFR (> 60)	0.369	1.447	0.474 – 4.417	0.516
Smoking	-16.846	0.000		1.000
Alcohol	0.226	1.253	0.370 – 4.238	0.717

Dependent variable: Uric acid level (Hyperuricaemia). BMI: body mass index; eGFR: estimated glomerular filtration rate

On multivariate regression analysis on hyperuricaemia on study group, age, sex, BMI eGFR, Smoking and Alcohol intake, predictors of hyperuricaemia in the study population include hypertension (OR = 5.677, 95% CI: 1.467 – 21.964; $p = 0.012$); gender (OR = 0.290, 95% CI: 0.088 – 0.951; $p = 0.041$) and obesity (OR = 4.669, 95% CI: 1.896 – 11.496; $p = 0.001$). (Table 4).

Discussion

In this present study, we determined the serum levels of uric acid in hypertensive patients and compared them with other cardiovascular risk factors. We observed a significantly higher serum levels of uric acid among the hypertensives than

the normotensive controls, implying a higher risk of cardiovascular disease in hypertensive patients. We also found a significant positive correlation between uric acid and BMI and WC in the hypertensive population and a significant positive correlation between uric acid and BMI in the controls. Also, predictors of hyperuricaemia in the study population included hypertension and obesity.

In accordance with our finding in this present study, several researchers have reported a higher prevalence of hyperuricaemia in hypertensive patients compared to normotensive controls. Prevalence rate of 18.2% was documented among hypertensive patients in Southwest China.¹⁷

Mishra et al, reported a prevalence of 26% in patients with hypertension.¹⁸ In a hospital-based cross-sectional study involving 168 hypertensive patients, prevalence of hyperuricaemia was 25%.¹⁹ Also, in a research undertaken to determine the prevalence of hyperuricaemia in 2145 hypertensive patients in Taiwan, a prevalence of 35% and 43% were reported in males and females respectively.²⁰ Studies done in other parts of Nigeria reported higher prevalence of hyperuricaemia in hypertensive patients. In a cross-sectional study among 150 newly diagnosed hypertensives in western part of Nigeria, prevalence of hyperuricaemia was 36.7%.²¹ In another Nigerian study including 130 newly diagnosed untreated hypertensive patients, a prevalence of 46.9% was recorded.²² The difference in prevalence between this present study and other Nigerian studies may be due to the several factors that affect serum uric acid levels including diet, drugs, alcohol, obesity, renal impairment, and hypertension.

The possible mechanism by which uric acid induces hypertension include stimulating the growth of vascular muscle cells, eliciting vascular inflammation, impairing endothelial cell function, inducing insulin resistance and activating renin-angiotensin system.²³

Similar to findings in this study, several researchers have reported a positive association between serum uric acid and BMI and WC. In a cross-sectional study including 260 Bangladeshi adults, there was a significant positive association between serum uric acid and obesity.²⁴ Haojie et al, reported a positive association between general obesity and central obesity with the prevalence of hyperuricaemia in a research involving 15,918 adults in China.²⁵ In another study to evaluate the association between obesity parameters and the risk of hyperuricaemia involving 17,753 adults, BMI and WC were positively associated with hyperuricemia.²⁶ Similarly, obesity was positively correlated with uric acid in a hospital-based cross-sectional study involving 150 outpatients.²⁷ Also, in a 10-year retrospective study in Chinese adults, serum uric acid was strongly correlated with BMI and WC.²⁸

In order to explain the potential mechanism linking serum uric acid and obesity, elevated serum uric acid has been suggested to accelerate hepatic and peripheral lipogenesis.²⁹ Also, it has

been documented that obesity and central fat distribution are linked with hyperuricaemia. In order to unravel the possible mechanism of this association, studies were carried out to assess the relationship between leptin and hyperuricaemia. It was reported that serum uric acid level was independently linked with the serum leptin level. The implication of this report is that leptin could be a pathogenic factor causing hyperuricaemia in cases of obesity.³⁰ Furthermore, WC and BMI are positively associated with insulin resistance and leptin level. Insulin resistance and leptin decreases renal uric acid excretion and uric acid is documented to cause insulin resistance.³¹

There are a few limitations. The study design is a cross-sectional study and cannot establish a causal relationship between serum uric acid and hypertension. Also, being a hospital-based study, it may not truly represent the population.

Conclusion

Serum uric acid levels were significantly higher in the hypertensive patients than in the normotensive controls, implying a higher risk of cardiovascular disease in hypertension. There was a significant positive correlation between uric acid and BMI and WC in the hypertensive population and a significant positive correlation between uric acid and BMI in the controls. Periodic measurement of serum uric acid is recommended in hypertensive and obese patients. This might be helpful to the clinicians in assessing the cardiovascular risk of the patient.

Declarations

Funding

This research was self-funded

Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest concerning this article.

Code availability

Not available

Authors' Contributions

AOB and DIM conceived the study. AOB, DIM and EMO reviewed the literature. AOB, DIM and EMO analysed the data. All the authors interpreted the data, drafted the manuscript, revised the data for sound intellectual content and approved the final version.

Ethics approval

Research was approved by the ethics and research committee of the Delta State Central Hospital, Warri.

Consent to participate

Written informed consent was obtained from each study participant.

Consent for publication

All authors approved the manuscript and gave consent for publication.

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